

Power Law Distribution, Impulse Relative to Energy and Fisher Information

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The power law probability distribution $P(e/T)$ proportional to $\{1-a(e/T)\}^k$ (power $1/k$), where k and a are constants, is experimentally observed in various scenarios, including stellar particles. As noted in (1), it is a solution of a Zwanzig differential equation with a dispersion term related to d/dp 's and a function $(1-be/T)$ as well as a friction term.

We note that unlike the conservation of energy i.e. $e_1+e_2=e_3$ in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, product probabilities seem to lead to the conservation of $\ln(1-ae/T)$, where $e=pp/2m + V(x)$. Writing $\ln(1-ae_1/T)+\ln(1-ae_2/T) = \ln(1-ae_3/T)$ and taking d/dx or alternatively d/dp leads to the conservation of relative terms i.e. $-dV/dx / (1-ae_1/T) -dV/dx / (1-ae_2/T) = -dV/dx / (1-ae_3/T)$ and $p_1/(1-ae_1/T) + p_2/(1-ae_2/T) = p_3/(1-ae_3/T)$. If p is thought of as an impulse, then $p/(1-ae/T)$ is an impulse relative to $1-ae/T$. For $V(x)\rightarrow 0$, one has $p/(1-pp/2mT)$ (nonrelativistically). We also note that relative type derivatives are closely linked to the Fisher statistical form: $I = \int dx P(x) \{d/dx \ln(P(x))\}^2$.

As a result, we transform the dispersion term in the Zwanzig equation into a function of Fisher information (integrand). We find that a term proportional to Fisher's information and a second term linked to the functional variation of Fisher's information (integrand) with respect to P appear as well as the friction term. As a result, this is a second differential equation which has a power law probability as a solution, and there might be some physical or statical reasons for writing an equation including Fisher's information related to relative derivatives.

Power Law Distribution and Conserved Quantity

In the case of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, $C \exp(-e/T)$, $\ln[P(e/T)]$, (called Shannon's information), is e/T dropping $\ln(C)$. "e" is also a conserved quantity and physical information in the problem. A power law distribution is:

$$P(e/T) \text{ proportional to } (1-ae/T)^{1/k} \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } k \text{ is a constant}$$

Taking \ln of a product of probabilities leads to $\ln(1-ae/T)$ being the conserved quantity which is quite different from the MB case. Taking either d/dx or d/dp of such an expression, with $e=pp/2m + V(x)$ (as in (1)) yields:

$$-dV/dx / (1-ae_1/T) - dV/dx / (1-ae_2/T) = -dV/dx / (1-ae_3/T) \quad ((2a))$$

$$p_1/(1-ae_1) + p_2/(1-ae_2/T) = p_3/(1-ae_3/T) \quad (2b))$$

Thus one has relative expressions. If p is considered to be proportional to impulse, one has "possibly" physical relative impulses i.e. $p_1/(1-ae_1/T)$ which show that simple Newtonian mechanics does not occur in whatever physical situation is present.

The reason we consider relative probabilities and derivatives is that these are closely related to the integrand of the statistical measure, Fisher's information:

$$I = \int dx P(x) \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P(x)) \right\} \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P(x)) \right\}. \quad ((3))$$

As a result, we speculate whether Fisher's information has a role to play in a power law distribution.

Power Law as a Solution of the Zwanzig Equation

In (1) it is stated that a power law distribution:

$$P(e/T) = C (1-k/T e)^{1/k} \quad ((4))$$

is a solution of the Zwanzig equation with dP/dt partial = 0, as one may verify:

$$dP/dt \text{ partial} = (-p/m) dP/dx + d/dp \{ dV/dx + p g(x,p) \} P + d/dp D(x,p) d/p P \quad ((5))$$

Where $d/dp = d/dp$ partial, $e=pp/2m+V(x)$ and $D(x,p) = gmT (1-ke/T)$ with $g(x,p)$ being related to friction ((6))

Given the relative nature of the derivatives dP/dx and dP/dp , we recast the last term on the RHS side or ((5)) in terms of Fisher's information. The power law distribution remains a solution, but it is possible that Fisher's information, which is a statistical quantity, may also somehow be linked to physical relative probabilities. This is speculation as it is not clear that the view of relative probabilities is directly linked to the physical nature of the problem. It may only be a mathematical view. We find:

$$D = gmT \exp\{ k \ln(P/C) \} \text{ and}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d/dp D(x,p) d/p P = & gmT \exp\{ k \ln(P/C) \} I (kc+1) + gmT \exp\{ k \ln(P/C) \} P d/dp (d \ln(P)/dp) \\ & + \{ (dg/dp) mT \exp\{ k \ln(P/C) \} \} P d \ln P / dp \end{aligned} \quad ((7))$$

Here I is the integrand of Fisher's information ((3)) with x replaced by p . One may note that ((7)) is written in terms of I , $\ln(P)$ and $d/dp (d \ln(P)/dp)$. The last term is reminiscent of a term which appears in quantum mechanics i.e. $d/dx d \ln W / dx = d/dx dW/dx / W - d \ln W / dx d \ln W / dx$ where $d/dx dW/dx$ is proportional to average kinetic energy, W being the wavefunction, and is also linked to Fisher's information, in fact to the functional variation of Fisher's information. In particular:

$$d/dp d \ln P / dp = d/dp dP/dp / P - \{ d \ln P / dp \} \{ d \ln P / dp \} \quad ((8))$$

Multiplying by P the last term of ((7)) becomes:

$$d/dp dP/dp - I \quad ((9))$$

Thus ((7)) is:

$$d/dp D(x,p) d/p P = gmT \exp\{ k \ln(P/C) \} \{ kcl + d/dp dP/dp + (d\ln(g)/dp) dP/dp \} \quad ((10))$$

The first term in {} is proportional to Fisher's information and the second is related to an extremized Fisher result (functionally extremized in terms of P). The principle of extreme information states that Fisher information should be extremized subject to constraints, so we argue that it is interesting that a term related to the extremized Fisher's information appears in ((10)). The only reason for writing the Zwanzig equation in terms of the statistical measure, Fisher's information, is that it might give insight to the physical situation in this problem and the idea of relative derivatives, in particular $d/dp \ln(e)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a power law distribution, $P(e/T)$ proportional to $(1-a(e/T))^{1/k}$ is linked with the conserved quantity $\ln(e)$ where $e = pp/2m + V(x)$. Taking either d/dx or d/dp of: $\ln(1-ae_1/T) + \ln(1-ae_2/T) = \ln(1-ae_3/T)$ yields relative terms such as $-dV/dx/(1-ae/T)$ or $p/(m(1-ae/T))$. We argue that such relative terms are reminiscent of the integrand of Fisher's information. It is stated in (1) that the power law distribution is a solution of the Zwanzig differential equation ((5)). We recast the last term of this first order differential equation in terms of Fisher's information, $\exp(\text{constant} \ln(P))$ and a term proportional to $d/dp d/dp P$ (reminiscent of the kinetic energy term in quantum mechanics and directly linked to a maximized Fisher term with respect to P as suggested by the principle of extreme information). The power law solution is then a solution of this second order differential equation in terms of these quantities which might shed some statistical and possibly physical light on the situation.

References

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